

ACTIVATION OF ASPECTUAL SEMANTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK NARRATIVE STRUCTURES

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Abstract:

The article analyzes the semantics of the narrative text from a theoretical point of view, and the relations of the world's leading linguists working in this field are studied. The personal relationship is expressed. The activation of temporal and aspectual features in the semantics of the narrative text is highlighted. Also, the views of the comparative and typological research of the pragmatic content of the text are included.

Key words: aspectual meaning, narrative text, semantics, temporal units.

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In the narrative text, limited events are expressed in the course of time, tenses have their own characteristics, and in discourse, tenses perform a deictic function and serve as an orientation to the moment of speech. [Smith, 2003; 109] In the narrative text, the features of limitation / non-limitation of realities are related to the eventfulness of the action or the completion or duration of the main part of the action. In these situations, there is no temporal limit. For example: After I quite my own mother stopped talking to me recalls one former broker who gave up after 3 months (Stone, 134).

In many narrative texts, events are associated with aspectual meanings such as the initial phase, duration, completion, aspiration to the final phase, a moment of action. Thus, aspectual meanings are directly related to the time course of reality in the narrative text. Therefore, aspectuality in English specifies not only the predicate, but also the space, time, and time of the realities in the text. For example: When you are done with the pitch simply say thank you and then goodbye.

It can be seen that in the English narrative text, temporal units as aspectual markers play an important role in changing the semantic meaning of predicates showing reality.

In addition to their aspectual aspect, it is considered that they serve to express transitive (transition- from one state to another state) or procedural (process- being in motion) semantic features, in addition to referring to the meaning of completion or process.

The lexical-grammatical category of actions interpreted within the framework of aspectual semantics is usually evaluated as a related phenomenon under the influence of predicates. But the semantics of the narrative text will have directly organized categorical indicators of behavior, types of behavior. In the general plan, the main types of behavior are introduced, such as nichiative, ingressive, durative, cognitive, semi-active, procedural, resultative. We will explain some of them. Mode of action that expresses the beginning (ingressive subtype, indicating the result in the occurrence of the action and its flow along with the beginning of the flow of action; inchoative subtype, indicating the starting point of the continuous action):

Completive mode of action (refers to the completion phase of the action):

Semeflective movement style: neutral group (represents one "quantum" of repeated movement. Movement metaphors are mainly divided into two types: phasic and processual. When phase movement is observed at the boundary of initiation or completion, procedural

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movement is considered the center of the movement flow and is carried out through the scanning path.

It is known that the lexical-semantic meanings of verbs are richer than words of other categories. Because their semantics may change depending on the lexical meaning of the component in the text in different situations during speech. In many cases, in narrative structures, successive realities represent a separate complex, event. In this case, it is necessary to refer to the analysis of the behavior of the verb.

Despite the fact that the predicates in this example appear in different positions, in different combinations with different lexical-semantic meanings, in the same text, regardless of the fact that they show different modes of action, such as stopped (perfective), scattered (distributive), relinquished (iterative), started back (inchoative) united. We can explain that the resulting meanings depend on the action, state and content of other signs of the components in the function of syntactic units, especially the situations related to the subject. It is noticeable that the temporal and aspectual meanings characteristic of the verb system in the English language are distinguished by the fact that they have a specific system that forms the content of the text.

According to A. Shermatov, it is important to refer to the lexico-centric and text-centric directions in the study of word semantics. [Shermatov A. About new directions in linguistics // New directions in linguistics and their problems. Materials of the scientific-practical seminar. -Tashkent, 2013. -B. 234-237.]. Therefore, it seems appropriate to follow the lexico-centric approach to determine the semantics of the behavior in the narrative text and the text centric approach to determine the aspectual characteristics. For example: A block or two north of the Park, Dawe steered the editor again eastward, then, after covering a short distance, into a lofty but narrow flat house burdened with a floridly over-decorated facade. To the fifth story they toiled, and Dawe, panting, pushed his latch-key into the door of one of the front flats (O'Henry, 337); 'When we gets in five hours of the country that we was going to introduce to long drinks and short change the captain calls us over to the starboard binnacle and recollects a few tilings. (O'Henry, 165) .

In the given examples, the predicate expressed by temporal indicators such as short distance, into a lofty but narrow flat house, over to the starboard indicates that the scope of action is limited. Therefore, in these examples, the predicate has limited semantics. It can be seen that the aspectual semantics of verbs in the function of predicates in the English narrative text in many cases depends on the semantic indicators of temporal conjunctions with prepositions in the text. In the Uzbek language, the activation of analytical compounds is observed. For example: People fell silent. The crackling of lanterns with darkened glass at the edges began to be clearly heard (O'tkir Hoshimov, 77). In this example, the analytic conjunctions became silent and began to be heard meant the aspectual semantics of the event. In this case, two opposing aspectual semantics, consequentiality and inchoative aspectual semantics, are activated. Let's look at the next example: I stayed at my aunt's house for three weeks on the pretext of a broken arm. At first, my father came every day. Then suddenly not a single one stopped coming (O'tkir Hoshimov, 134). In linguistics, it is widely recognized that the functional aspect of language is related to the activation of units in the text. Because the activation of the language in the text is also related to its functional side. The verb, which plays an important role in the functionality of the language, differs from other groups of words in terms of its polysemy, variety in form formation, richness, formation of compounds and differentiation of meanings in them, as well as the ability to change meaning. In order to determine the complex of meanings and lexical-semantic meanings of verbs, their classification is important.

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